

**ΕΛΛΗΝΙΚΗ ΕΠΙΤΡΟΠΗ ΤΟΥ ΔΙΕΘΝΟΥΣ ΣΥΜΒΟΥΛΙΟΥ
ΜΕΓΑΛΩΝ ΗΛΕΚΤΡΙΚΩΝ ΔΙΚΤΥΩΝ**

Πειραιώς 45, 105 53, Αθήνα, Τηλ.-Fax: 210-3216851, e-mail: contact@cigre.gr

COMITÉ NATIONAL HELLENIQUE

45, rue Pireos, 105 53, Athènes, Tel.-Fax: +30210-3216851, e-mail: contact@cigre.gr

GREEK NATIONAL COMMITTEE

45, Pireos Str., 105 53, Athens, Tel.-Fax: +30210-3216851, e-mail: contact@cigre.gr

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**Enhancing Transmission Power System Reliability through the
Activation of Distribution Network Flexibilities**

M. C. Sousounis¹
IPTO

P. Dratsas
IPTO

C. Kaskouras
IPTO

A. Bachoumis
IPTO

C. Dikaiakos
IPTO

G. Papaioannou
IPTO

ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the potential future breakthroughs of TSO/DSO coordination in enhancing the transmission system reliability without further extensions or upgrades of the power system infrastructure. The demonstration site of Kefalonia is selected for the case study. Simulations are carried out through PSS[®]E in order to investigate the prospects of dealing with voltage violations and congestions problems in the transmission system through flexibilities provided by assets of the distribution network. The data and future projections used for the simulations were retrieved from IPTO and ENTSO-E databases. Results show that overvoltages can be successfully mitigated by increasing the absorbed apparent power of the distribution system. Moreover, a congestion management solution is proposed during N-1 conditions at the transmission lines of Ionian islands. By appropriately managing the flexibility assets of the distribution system at Kefalonia, congestion violations at the Zante – Kyllini transmission line can be resolved.

¹e-mail: m.sousounis@admie.gr

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Ενέργειας Μέσω των Δυνατοτήτων Ευελιξίας του Δικτύου Διανομής**

Μ. Χ. Σουσουίνης¹
ΑΔΜΗΕ

Π. Δράτσας
ΑΔΜΗΕ

Χ. Κασκούρας
ΑΔΜΗΕ

Α. Μπαχούμης
ΑΔΜΗΕ

Χ. Δικαϊάκος
ΑΔΜΗΕ

Γ. Παπαϊωάννου
ΑΔΜΗΕ

ΠΕΡΙΛΗΨΗ

Η παρούσα εργασία επικεντρώνεται στις δυνατότητες συνεργασίας μεταξύ διαχειριστών μεταφοράς και διανομής για την ενίσχυση της αξιοπιστίας του συστήματος μεταφοράς, χωρίς περαιτέρω επεκτάσεις ή αναβαθμίσεις υποδομής του συστήματος ηλεκτρικής ενέργειας. Το νησί της Κεφαλονιάς έχει επιλέγει για την διεξαγωγή της μελέτης. Οι προσομοιώσεις γίνονται στο προγραμματιστικό περιβάλλον PSS@E προκειμένου να διερευνηθούν οι προοπτικές αντιμετώπισης των παραβιάσεων τάσης και των προβλημάτων συμφόρησης στο σύστημα μεταφοράς, μέσω των δυνατοτήτων ευελιξίας που παρέχονται από το δίκτυο διανομής. Τα δεδομένα και οι μελλοντικές προβλέψεις που χρησιμοποιήθηκαν για τις προσομοιώσεις ανακτήθηκαν από τις βάσεις δεδομένων του ΙΠΤΟ και του ENTSO-E. Τα αποτελέσματα δείχνουν ότι οι υπερτάσεις μπορούν να αντιμετωπιστούν επιτυχώς αυξάνοντας την απορροφούμενη φαινόμενη ισχύ του συστήματος διανομής. Επιπλέον, προτείνεται μια λύση διαχείρισης συμφόρησης κατά τη διάρκεια N-1 κατάστασης στις γραμμές μεταφοράς των Ιονίων Νήσων. Με την κατάλληλη διαχείριση της ευελιξίας του συστήματος διανομής στην Κεφαλονιά, μπορούν να επιλυθούν υπερφορτίσεις στη γραμμή μεταφοράς Ζάκυνθος - Κυλλήνη.

¹e-mail: m.sousounis@admie.gr

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing deployment of Renewable Energy Sources (RES), as well as the visions of decarbonization of the European energy system by 2050 [1], [2], dictate the need to seriously examine the reliability of power systems using innovative flexibility entities. Demand Side (DS) response schemes, small-scale RES generation and energy storage systems (ESS) should be able to guarantee the provision of flexibility services, such as balancing, voltage regulation, congestion management, controlled islanding, inertial response and black start, in order to enhance their role to power system reliability and decrease the investments in conventional fossil fuel generation units or the expansion of contemporary power grids [3]. To achieve this, Transmission System Operators (TSO) and Distribution System Operators (DSO) must go beyond their separate functionalities and act in a coordinated manner, something that is also highlighted from ENTSO-E [4], [5].

The CoordiNet project, primarily aims to demonstrate how TSO and DSO shall act in a coordinated manner to procure and activate the aforementioned grid services in the most reliable and efficient way. For this scope, ten (10) large-scale demonstrations will take place in three different European countries, Greece, Spain and Sweden, in order to develop and implement data exchange platforms between TSO and DSO to identify and address power system problems [6].

Two of those demonstrations will be held in Greece with the collaboration of IPTO, HEDNO, ICCS and ETRA and specifically in two different areas, Kefalonia island and Mesogia area. Services regarding voltage control and congestion management will be explored during that particular demonstration. The four distinct domains which will participate in the Greek Demonstrations are the Transmission System Operator, the Distribution System Operator, the data exchange platform (developed particularly for the Project's purposes), which will be called CoordiNet platform, and the Flexibility Service Providers (FSP). The CoordiNet platform is an interface that is intended to manage different interactions between the TSO, DSO and Flexibility Service Providers (FSP). The basic functionalities for which CoordiNet platform is responsible for are the detection and the identification of grid disturbances and violations, the selection of the appropriate agents to provide the necessary flexibility and the immediate dispatch of orders to them. A specific market model must also be applied in CoordiNet platform for the compensation of FSP and the greater engagement of consumers and aggregators [7].

Initiated by the above described scope of the CoordiNet project in Greece, this paper investigates the way that flexibility provided by the distribution network can be leveraged to alleviate potential problems that may appear at the transmission System, namely line congestions and voltage violations. Simulations are carried out through an appropriate transmission system planning software tool (PSS[®]E[8]), in order to investigate the possibility of dealing with the problems emerging in the transmission system through flexibilities provided by the assets of the distribution system. Our study takes into consideration the expected increase of demand load and RES penetration, based on IPTO's load demand and RES production forecast studies[9], in order to examine the problems, and in turn the flexibility needs for a specific area in the Greek power system. Finally, guidelines for the utilization of the distribution system flexibilities by the transmission system operator are proposed. Specifically, in section 4.1 a map of voltage reduction at the HV side of Argostoli substation is plotted as a function of active and reactive power distribution system flexibilities at the MV side of Argostoli substation. Regarding congestion management at the transmission system of Ionian Islands, different scenarios are explored in section 4.2 which can employ distribution system flexibilities but system reconfiguration as well when voltage violations are detected due to the activation of distribution system flexibilities.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Existing Solutions

Voltage control and congestion management are two key services for the reliable operation of power systems [10]. To date, in Greece conventional ways to deal with voltage violations and congestion problems are adopted in the transmission system. Especially, regarding voltage control, system operator (SO) applies dispatch instructions in order to regulate reactive power generation and uses reactive power leading or lagging compensation apparatus. Concerning real-time congestion management, after detecting congestion problems system operator solves them manually through the activation of interruptible loads. The aforementioned

practices ensure safe and secure operation of the system not in the most efficient way. The high infrastructure requirements and the probability of loss of load are their main drawbacks. This is the reason why alternative ways to deal with these problems should be investigated.

2.2 Market-based solution

Flexibilities provided from distribution system may seem decisive for the resolution of voltage violations and congestion problems. A market-based solution will replace the need of TSO to invest in infrastructure reinforcement [11]. Thus, it is important to quantify the necessary flexibility required by the transmission system operator to alleviate its problems. Two approaches are presented for each problem case.

Voltage Control: System operator has to ask for the appropriate amount of power necessary for the mitigation of voltage violations, through the CoordiNet platform. SO detects the system load conditions under which violations occur, and subsequently requests for power exchange in order to resolve them, without at the same time violating any of the system safety and security constraints.

This paper specifically focuses on overvoltages and how can be handled by considering the absorption of apparent power with a capacitive power factor ranging from 0.9 to 1. This kind of flexibility can be provided by DERs that have smart converters[12], thus being capable of providing also reactive power. Flexibility can be given by DERs of the following type:

- a. PV panels.
- b. Wind farms
- c. Electric Vehicles (V2G technology) and battery storage systems.
- d. Pumped storage hydroelectricity.
- e. Industrial or consumer demand response.

Congestion Management: The hosting capacity of a given grid is limited by the inherent characteristics of physical assets (i.e. lines, cables, transformers). Congestion is a condition where one or more constraints (thermal limits, voltage limits, stability limits) restrict the physical power flow through the network. In case of congestion problems at the transmission system in near-real time operation, SO asks through the CoordiNet platform for apparent power provision. The assets mentioned in the case of voltage control can also be leveraged to provide this service for the transmission system.

2.3 Assumptions

In this paper the following assumptions are considered:

1. Problems regarding congestion management and voltage control on the level of TS are only investigated. Problems arising in the distribution grid are not examined in this study. Hence, it is considered that the flexibility provided by DERs is rigorously coordinated, thus avoiding congestion and voltage violation problem in the level of the distribution network.
2. Regarding the voltage violations, in the 150kV (1 pu) level of the transmission system, overvoltages exist over 162kV (over 1.05pu) and undervoltages under 142.5kV (under 0.95pu) threshold. Congestion problems exist when the current exceeds the 85% of the rated value [13].
3. The type of DER used for the provision of flexibility services is out of the scope of this paper. Technical characteristics such as activation time and ramp-up are excluded. The only parameter that is considered is the power, either active or reactive, that DERs of a particular area in an aggregated manner can provide. For example, demand response through water heating can provide only active power (resistive load). Demand response through machines increase both active and reactive power, based on a power factor. Therefore, the flexibility provided by assets connected to the distribution network is modelled as a black box.
4. TSO/DSO/Aggregators/Consumers data and bid exchange, and flexibility market clearance are excluded from this work. Indicative information about the coordination and market platform can be found in the deliverables of the CoordiNet project [11].
5. PSS®E is used for the simulations, and full Newton-Raphson power flow method is performed.

3. CASE STUDY

3.1 Topology

In this paper, the case study is conducted in one of the demonstration sites, namely Kefalonia island. Figure 1 illustrates the transmission system topology in the broader area. There are two HV/MV substations located on the island of Kefalonia. The Argostoli substation services the entire load of Kefalonia whereas Myrtos substation is used for RES connections. The research study of activating flexibilities at the distribution system is conducted at the substation of Argostoli but the broader area, from Kyllini to Aktio, is monitored for violations. Figure 2 presents the single line diagram of Argostoli substation. At the HV side, the transmission system connections to Myrtos and Zante substations can be identified as well as the passive inductive components which are currently being used to regulate voltage. At the MV side, the distribution network of Kefalonia consists of twelve 20kV feeders that serve several locations on the island.

Figure 1: Map of Transmission System in Kefalonia.

Figure 2: Single line diagram for Argostoli substation.

3.2 Problems in the area

Through a rigorous analysis of historical data, the voltage violations at the HV side of Argostoli substation mainly concern the violation of the upper permitted voltage limit ($162\text{kV} / 1.08\text{pu}$). These overvoltages occur during low demand periods and the reasons behind this are listed below:

- Cables extent and length: The two HV submarine cables which connect Kefalonia with the nearby islands of Zante and Lefkada, as well as the great length of overhead transmission and distribution lines, are responsible for the increased reactive power flow. Today, the reactive power lagging compensation apparatus is used in order to deal with this problem.
- Hydro plant operation: The Western part of the Greek interconnected power system, has a large number of hydro plants which contribute to the control of the system voltage. When these hydro plants shut down or remain offline, usually in low demand periods, voltage fluctuations are increased.
- Interconnection with Italy: The HVDC system for the nearby interconnection of the Greek TS with Italy provides reactive power to the grid of western Greek system. Consequently, this is an additional reason why overvoltages appear in this region [14].

Congestion problems and transmission lines overloading events are not presented under normal operating conditions for the power system of Kefalonia. Even at the island's high demand periods or peak demand hours the system components respond smoothly and thermal limits on equipment are not violated. This is the reason

why congestion or overloading problems are examined under N-1 conditions, by considering that line connecting Aktio to Lefkada is out of operation.

3.3 Simulation scenarios

Different set of scenarios are simulated in PSSE to investigate the flexibility impact on solving the problems existing in the transmission system. Figure 3 (left) presents a snapshot of the under-study power system under normal conditions, during high season.

Figure 3: Snapshot of the Ionian Islands power system during high season.
(Left): Normal operation. (Right): N-1 Conditions

Regarding the case of overvoltages, a real snapshot of the power system has been utilized. Specifically, a case of low load in Kefalonia island where overvoltages do exist at the HV side (150kV) of Argostoli substation (Figure 4). Then, simulations take place for different provided flexibility amounts in MVA, for a range of power factor values to assess the direct impact that flexibility has on voltage reduction in transmission system. As depicted in Figure 4 the activated flexibility is connected to the MV side of Argostoli substation.

Figure 4: Snapshot of the Kefalonia power system during low demand. Overvoltage appears at the HV side of Argostoli substation.

Regarding the case of congestion violations, three scenarios depicting three different years, namely 2020, 2025 and 2030, are simulated. Projections made by IPTO about Ionian islands' load and RES installed capacity have been utilized for the last two studied years. For all these scenarios, congestion is investigated during a high season evening, mid of August, with low RES production due to the zero PV production (Figure 3(right)). In addition, in the case of 2030 a new 150kV line connecting Kefalonia to Lefkada has been introduced and the 150kV submarine line connecting Kyllini to Zante has been upgraded by 50MVA to achieve a rated capacity of 200MVA. Both future infrastructure reinforcements have been proposed in the 10-year Development Plan[15]. By combining all the above-mentioned data, simulations are carried out to investigate how distribution network flexibility in MVA, can solve congestion problems existing in the transmission system. Due to the increased complexity that is introduced in the congestion management, network reconfiguration (utilizing existing assets of the transmission system, such as inductors) is also implemented in the simulation model.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Voltage control

In this case, a real system snapshot where low-load conditions appear is utilized. This corresponds to an early morning day during the beginning of spring, which means an off-season for the broader area of Ionian islands. Low-load demand and medium RES generation causes overvoltages in the HV bus in Argostoli substation. According to the standard practices, the TSO will alleviate those voltage violations (more than 1.08pu), by introducing passive inductive components connected to the HV bus of Argostoli (Figure 4). In this paper, we introduce an alternative approach to the normal practice of the TSO.

Figure 5 illustrates the amount of distribution system flexibility needed to reduce the voltage in the HV bus as a function of the incremental absorption of apparent power (MVA) and its inductive power factor value. Specifically, a range of up to 20 MVA distribution system flexibility was selected, which is approximately 36% of the peak apparent power demand at Argostoli substation. As expected, the power factor value affects significantly the flexibility amount needed; less amount is necessary for lower inductive power factor values to achieve the same voltage reduction. For example, if 2kV (0.013pu) voltage reduction is necessary to set voltage level in HV bus less than 162kV (1.08pu), either flexibility of 19.6MW is needed or 12.4MVA of inductive power factor 0.9.

Figure 5 can be used as an initial roadmap for TSOs to utilize the distribution network flexibilities for voltage control services. Further research can be carried out to explore the flexibility impact on different HV substation topologies, or to explore the contribution of the neighboring areas flexibility to solve voltage violation problems.

Figure 5: Voltage reduction in High Voltage Bus based on flexibility characteristics.

4.2 Congestion Management

For the congestion management case study, three years have been simulated: 2020, 2025, and 2030. Each one includes different load values, RES production data, and future infrastructure reinforcements, based on real data and projections made by IPTO. In all the scenarios, congestion has been investigated in two HV lines, namely Zante-Argostoli connection and Zante-Kyllini, under N-1 conditions, in a high season evening with low RES production. Particularly, the line connecting Aktio to Lefkada has been out of operation in the simulation model. Only the flexibility provided by the distribution network connected to the Argostoli substation is considered in the analysis.

The solution of congestion problems can be considered significantly more complex than the solution of voltage violation problems. In order to eliminate the congestion in a particular line, the apparent power flowing in that line has to be decreased by reducing the total demand of the distribution side from the main grid. However, as the total demand of the distribution side reduces the voltage at the HV side increases, which may lead to additional problems in the system. This issue can be tackled either by reducing the total demand of the distribution side with an inductive power factor or in the case that only active power flexibility exists, network reconfiguration has to take place.

Figure 6 presents the congestion management in the Zante-Kyllini line for three different years (2020, 2025, 2030) based on IPTO projections. As mentioned above, the congestion is tackled through two different approaches. The solid line illustrates the case in which the total demand of the distribution side at Argostoli substation is reduced with an inductive power factor 0.9, whereas the dashed line presents the case in which only the flexibility of active power exists. In both 2020 and 2025 cases, under N-1 condition, congestion reaches approximately 98% of the rated Ampere. The high congestion percentage is due to the fact that Zante-Kyllini line services the high season loads of three islands: Zante, Kefalonia and Lefkada. As the flexibility amount increases, the congestion at Zante-Kyllini line drops. In the case where the flexibility has an inductive power factor of 0.9, the decrease of congestion is linear and reaches approximately 80% for a 20MVA amount. On the other hand, when only active power is activated (dashed line), a steeper linear decrease is observed, until reconfiguration is needed. Reconfiguration takes place twice in order to keep the voltage of the HV bus in the Argostoli substation within normal operational limits (0.95pu-1.08pu). In both of the approaches, at 20MVA used flexibility, similar congestion level is achieved. In 2030, due to the grid reinforcements described in section 3.3, the initial congestion is lower, approximately 80%. At 20MVA used flexibility, congestion reaches

68% and 65%, with the lower congestion outcome appearing in the case of flexibility with inductive power factor 0.9.

Figure 6: Simulation results for congestion management in Zante- Kyllini connection, under N-1 conditions.

Figure 7: Simulation results for congestion management in Zante-Argostoli connection, under N-1 conditions.

Figure 7 illustrates the results in Zante-Argostoli line for the three different years. Compared to Figure 6, Zante-Argostoli line has a lower initial congestion level, approximately 75%, because of the fact that services two islands, namely Kefalonia and Lefkada. Hence, only in the line Argostoli-Kyllini (Figure 6) severe congestion issues arise. The aim of this paper is to primarily solve the congestion issues in the lines that there is a higher hazard to be present. The results of this line are included in order to provide a complete view of the congestion management approach, and its effect in neighboring lines. Similarly, to Zante-Kyllini line, when flexibility with a power factor of 0.9 is enabled, linear decrease in congestion level also takes place. In contrast, when flexibility with unity power factor is used, there is a lower rate of congestion reduction until reconfiguration takes place. At reconfiguration instances, the congestion level drops significantly. This is due to the fact that

passive inductors are connected to the HV bus of Argostoli substation, which absorb the excessive reactive power flowing towards the line. As a general remark it can be observed that in that line, active flexibility together with reconfiguration achieves a better result than flexibility with inductive power factor 0.9.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, alternative ways to enhance the transmission system are presented by exploiting distribution system flexibilities. The case study of Kefalonia was selected due to the potential future issues that may arise with the increased RES generation and the high-season demand. The two main services the TSO has to provide are voltage control and congestion management. Regarding voltage control, overvoltages were explored due to their appearance during off-season. A key contribution of this paper is the initial roadmap that was generated which can be used for TSO-DSO coordination to utilize the distribution network flexibilities for voltage control services. The graph of voltage reduction as a function of the apparent power can be utilized to estimate flexibility needs for all voltage control services. Further research can be carried out to explore the flexibility impact on different HV substation topologies, or to explore the contribution of the neighboring areas flexibility to solve voltage violation problems. Regarding congestion management, the congested line was not directly connected to the substation where flexibilities were activated. Despite that, this research paper shows that congestion can be reduced through distribution system flexibilities from nearby substations, but care has to be taken in order to avoid overvoltages due to the decrease of the demand. In addition, neighboring lines have to be monitored cause the direction of flow of reactive power can have a significant impact on the connected substations and the congestion of the line. Future research for congestion management will focus on dispersing the activated flexibilities in order to avoid the use of passive inductive apparatus.

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